

2. Bromocresol-treated filter paper that has not (left) and that has (right) been exposed to brown planthopper honeydew.

5 hours, are allowed to feed for 24 hours. Honeydew excreted by BPH is absorbed on the filter paper. After the feeding duration, the filter paper is removed and treated with 0.001% ninhydrin in acetone solution and oven-dried at 100°C for 5 minutes. The honeydew spots appear as

violet or purple because of their amino acid content. The area of ninhydrin-positive spots is traced on paper and placed on millimeter-square graph. The squares are then counted. (Spots must be traced within a few days because they fade rapidly.)

The technique has been modified to estimate BPH feeding activity during the feeding period as the filter papers are treated before placement in the feeding chamber and spots appear as soon as the honeydew makes contact. The new technique is a modification of that used in aphid feeding studies using filter papers treated with bromocresol blue. Whatman No. 1 filter paper is impregnated twice with bromocresol green solution (2 mg/ml ethanol). The filter paper is allowed to dry for 1 hour, then re-treated with the solution. This turns the filter paper to orange. Insects are placed in the feeding chamber through a hole at the top, which is then plugged with cotton (photo 1). The filter paper is removed 24 hours later (photo 2). The stained filter paper can be stored as long as 3 months after the test, or until enough time is available to trace the spots and measure their area. The treated filter paper should not be moistened because water can cause spots to form. ■

Soil and crop management

Effect of seed pretreatment on rainfed dryland rice production and on water saturation deficit in leaves

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The effects of seed pretreatment on germinability, plant growth, and grain production in direct-seeded dryland rice were studied during three seasons from 1976 to 1979. In laboratory trials, the increases in shoot length (16 to 48%) and root length (5 to 33%) at 4 and 6 days after the start of the experiments were significant. In field experiments, the plants grown from pretreated seeds significantly outscored those from untreated seeds in plant height and population per unit area. The increases in tiller number per unit area of the pretreated vs untreated seeds (control) were 22% when seeds were pretreated

Table 1. Effects of seed treatments on grain yields of rice varieties (V) at 14% moisture. West Bengal, India.

Seed treatment (T)	Grain yields (t/ha)									
	1976				1977			1978		
	IET 2914	Dular	IR442-58	Mean	IET 2914	Dular	Mean	IET 2914	Dular	Mean
Control (untreated)	1.8	1.7	1.7	1.7	1.9	1.8	1.9	1.9	1.8	1.8
Soaking in distilled water										
24 h	1.9	1.8	1.9	1.9	2.4	2.2	2.3	2.2	2.1	2.2
48 h	2.0	1.9	2.0	1.9	2.4	2.3	2.4	2.2	2.2	2.2
24 h double ^a	1.9	1.8	1.9	1.9	2.3	2.1	2.2	2.0	2.0	2.0
NaCl	1.8	1.8	1.8	1.8	2.4	2.1	2.2	2.1	2.1	2.1
NaH ₂ PO ₄	2.0	1.9	1.9	1.9	2.4	2.2	2.3	2.2	2.2	2.2
Na ₂ HPO ₄	2.1	2.0	2.0	2.0	2.5	2.3	2.4	2.3	2.3	2.3
Al(NO ₃) ₃	1.9	1.9	1.9	1.9	2.3	2.2	2.3	2.2	2.1	2.1
CoNO ₃	1.9	1.8	1.9	1.9	2.4	2.1	2.3	2.0	2.1	2.0
Agromin	1.9	1.8	1.8	1.8	2.4	2.1	2.2	2.2	2.0	2.1
Fungicide treated	1.8	1.8	1.8	2.1	1.9	2.0	2.0	2.0	2.0	2.0
Mean	1.9	1.8	1.9	1.8	2.3	2.1	2.2	2.1	2.1	2.1
	V	T	V x T	V	T	V x T	V	T	V x T	
S Em (±)	0.01	0.03	0.03	0.04	0.03	0.05	0.05	0.06		0.08
CD at 5%	0.05	0.07		0.12	0.09			0.16		
CV		7.0			15.0			19.4		

^aThe 24-h soaking was repeated.

with Na₂HPO₄(10⁻³ m) in 358 ppm solution for 6 hours; 22% with soaking

in 200 ppm solution of Agromin (a chemical formulation consisting of

7 nutrient ingredients — Zn, Fe, Cu, Mn, Mg, B, Mo in chelated form) for 20 hours; and 18% with $\text{Al}(\text{NO}_3)_3$ in 200 ppm solution for 20 hours. Before planting, the treated seeds were sun-dried to their original moisture status. The increases in plant dry-matter accumulation ranged from 13 to 54%. Ash-free root weights also increased (13 to 63%); the increments over the control treatment were 63% with Na_2HPO_4 , 40% with NaH_2PO_4 , 40% with $\text{Al}(\text{NO}_3)_3$, and 37% with water soaking. The last treatment consisted of soaking seeds in distilled water for 24 or 48 hours and then drying to the original moisture status (“24 hours double” means that the 24-hour soaking was repeated). All seeds except those in the untreated control were treated with fungicide (Agrosan at 2 g/kg). Grain yields were 14 to 26% higher in crops raised from pretreated seeds (Table 1). The seeds were treated with NaCl (38 ppm for 6 hours), NaH_2PO_4 (156 ppm for 6 hours), and CoNO_3 (200 ppm for 20 hours) solutions and then dried to original moisture level. Close and significant relationships were found for grain yield and root-to-shoot ratio ($r = 0.86$), percentage of total available carbohydrate (TAC) in roots ($r = 0.90$), ash-free

Table 2. Water saturation deficit in leaves and ash-free root weight of rice varieties (V) at 30-45 cm depth, 50 days after sowing. West Benzal, India.

Seed treatment (T)	Water saturation deficit (%)			Decrease (%) from control	Ash-free root wt (mg/5 cm diam cylindrical core)			Increase (%) over control
	IET 2914	Dular	Mean		IET 2914	Dular	Mean	
	Control (untreated)	20.9	17.4		19.1		42	
Soaking in distilled water								
24 h	19.2	12.7	16.0	17	50	57	53	37
48 h	18.2	13.3	15.7	18	87	50	68	75
24 h double ^a	17.3	13.8	15.6	19	62	61	62	58
NaCl	17.0	13.7	15.5	19	37	48	42	9
NaH_2PO_4	15.6	15.5	15.6	19	75	47	61	56
Na_2HPO_4	14.8	12.8	13.8	28	86	60	73	86
$\text{Al}(\text{NO}_3)_3$	15.9	14.5	15.2	21	52	71	61	57
CoNO_3	18.5	14.3	16.3	15	60	62	61	56
Agromin	16.3	13.3	14.8	23	68	50	59	51
Fungicide treated	18.0	16.5	17.3	10	62	31	46	19
Mean	15.5	14.3			63	52		
	V	T	V x T		V	T	V x T	
S Em (\pm)	1.0	0.7	1.2		7.4	8.1	11.5	
CD at 5%		2.0				23.0		

^aThe 24-h soaking was repeated.

deep-root weight ($r = 0.79$), and water saturation deficit in leaves ($r = -0.66$ for IET2914 and -0.74 for Dular). The relationships were also close and significant for shallow root (0–15 cm) weight and TAC content ($r = 0.79$); deep root (15–45 cm) weight and water saturation deficit ($r = -0.78$); and chlorophyll stability index and root weight ($r = -0.78$).

The increased vigor of the plants from pretreated seeds was due mainly to the better root growth, particularly of deep roots, which decreased the water saturation deficit (Table 2) and chlorophyll stability index values of leaves. The roots and shoots of plants from pretreated seeds also contained more TAC. ■

Time of fertilizer nitrogen application in rice culture

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The notoriously low utilization of fertilizer nitrogen by rice is thought to be largely caused by nitrogen losses in the soil-plant system. Of the various factors that affect nitrogen efficiency, the time of application is important. After transplanting, rice seedlings take a few days to recover (the “transplanting shock period”), and then start growing. Nitrogen applied during this period may be poorly utilized by the plants and much is probably lost to leaching, denitrification, and volatilization.

A field experiment was conducted during summer (Apr-Jun), 1978, to determine the best time of first nitrogen

Total nitrogen content (%)

Relationship between nitrogen content of the rice plant and days after transplanting. Ludhiana, India.

application to rice for higher yields. The soil — Fatehpur loamy sand — had a pH of 8.1 and was low in organic carbon. After transplanting, rice seedling samples were taken daily from selected treatments for 9 days and analyzed for total nitrogen content using the Technicon Nitrogen Autoanalyzer

following the 1966 technique of Warner and Jones.

The nitrogen content of rice plants tended to decrease during the first 4 days after transplanting (see figure). A gradual increase on the 5th and 6th days of sampling was followed by a sharp decline. The differential nitrogen